

INTelligent, ACTIVE MicroBIOME-based, biodegradable PACKaging for Mediterranean food INTACTBIOPACK	
Project summary	<p>INTACTBioPack is a 36 months-time frame project, involving a multi-disciplinary consortium of 11 partners that aims to foster the adoption by the Mediterranean region, of novel, cost-competitive, biodegradable, and reusable food packaging solutions by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Developing innovative home-compostable food-packaging materials, covering the dual functions of protective barrier and active food ingredient, as well as a reusable sensor (vegetal layer coupled with low-cost RFID) and colorimetric sensor to monitor food freshness during storage and at home. 2. Exploring the potentialities of bio- and microbiome-based solutions to design alternatives to synthetic/chemical based-solutions, and to develop consumer “self-packing” solutions to preserve or upcycle at-home leftovers or unconsumed but still edible raw fresh produce. 3. Enabling a general strategy for designing safe, sustainable, and efficient biodegradable, active packaging solutions by the deployment of generalised methodologies, mathematical tools, business plans and guidelines
Project objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Endow the Mediterranean food industry with a range of home-compostable, anti-microbials- and microbiome-based packaging solutions with tailored functionalities that match specific food requirements (quality and safety preservation) and are in line with food contact material legislation (chemical migration), • Set up an operational framework for designing safe, sustainable, and efficient active packaging solutions adapted to food needs, technical and social constraints • Enable simple and fair tracking of food freshness status at home and in the food supply chain using low-cost colorimetric and RFID-based sensors • Build a co-creation process to bridge the gap between the food packaging chain diverse players (R&D, food and packaging industry and citizens) to fast track-the use and acceptability of innovative bio-, active and intelligent food packaging solutions in the Mediterranean region • Carry out assessment of the benefits of the developed innovative packaging in reducing FWL in the Mediterranean regions, thus limiting economic and environmental impact of the food/packaging system as a whole • Promote the project, communicate, and disseminate into society the benefit of project solutions through the setting-up of dedicated dissemination to gain consumer’s and market’s trust into bio-, active and smart packaging
Countries involved	<p>France, Croatia, Portugal, Algeria, Turkey, Italy, Egypt, Tunisia, Spain</p>